

ISSUES OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOIL AND PLANT BIOMICROELEMENT COMPOSITION AND CROP QUALITY

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Abstract. *This article analyzes how the biomicronnutrient composition of soil and plants affects crop quality. The main chemical microelements in the soil (copper, zinc, boron, molybdenum) are considered among the key factors influencing plant development and the nutritional value of agricultural products. The presence of adequate levels of proteins, starch, fats, carbohydrates, and vitamins in agricultural products—meeting human dietary needs—is closely tied to the composition and concentration of chemical elements in the soil. Based on the collected data, practical recommendations have been developed for producing high-quality and environmentally friendly products through proper management of the chemical composition of soil and plants. This research is useful for defining promising strategies in agriculture aimed at increasing soil fertility and improving crop yields.*

Keywords: *biomicronnutrient, migration, concentration, soil fertility, norm, vitamin, Clark, accumulation, province.*

Introduction

On February 2, 2024, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan N. 903 "On Protecting Soil and Increasing Its Fertility" was adopted [1]. A key task set for our scientists in this regard is enriching soils with humus and essential chemical nutrients.

The chemical composition of soil and plants is closely interrelated and is one of the main factors directly influencing productivity and product quality in agriculture. Plant development, as well as their biological, chemical, and nutritional value, largely depends on the soil's mineral composition, the quantity of nutrients it contains, and the plants' ability to absorb them.

The main components of soil—nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium determine plant growth, fruit formation, and the overall quality indicators of the yield. In addition, micronutrients in the soil play a significant role in the formation of enzymes, vitamins, proteins, and fructose in plants. Soil properties such as pH level, salt content, and the amount of organic matter also significantly affect the chemical composition and quality of plants.

In modern agriculture, great attention is being paid to improving the quality of products and growing nutrient-rich foods that are safe for human health. Therefore, the importance of determining the chemical state of the soil, maintaining its fertility, and providing plants with proper nutrition is steadily increasing.

According to international dietitians, at least 50% of the food consumed by humans should consist of fruits and vegetables. These products are rich in beneficial micronutrients, and historically, Avicenna (Ibn Sina) used fruits and vegetables to treat various illnesses, as chemical

medications were not available at that time, and patients were treated with natural remedies. These included vegetables, fruits, herbs, and various plants.

To ensure sufficient food supply for the population, it is necessary to rethink food systems and agriculture, including attitudes toward soil and plant life. This is because substances beneficial or harmful to human health enter plants through the soil and migrate through the chain:

Soil → Plant → Food Product → Human Body.

LITERATURE REVIEW

V.I. Vernadsky emphasized that, when classifying elements, it is necessary to consider their most important properties and characteristics in the Earth's crust. He highlighted aspects such as mobility, mineral formation capability, and radioactivity [2].

A.A. Kist, in his work, classified elements into constitutional, irreplaceable, less-studied, and unstudied categories. Elements such as B, F, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Br, Mo, and I were described as irreplaceable micronutrients [3]. Of course, many elements from D.I. Mendeleev's periodic table are found in soil, animal life, water, the atmosphere, and plants.

Boron (B) is considered an irreplaceable element for plant life and function, as well as for the animal world. Although boron is not part of the composition of enzymes, it enhances their activity. An excess amount of boron increases the intensity of metabolic processes, but it is toxic in high concentrations. Boron poisoning leads to the release of large amounts of phosphorus.

The total boron content in soil ranges between 2×10^{-3} and $1.6 \times 10^{-3}\%$, while its mobile fractions are between 1.9×10^{-5} and $1.1 \times 10^{-4}\%$ [4]. The biogeochemical properties of boron are described in the works of A.E. Fersman [5] and V.I. Vernadsky [2]. According to these authors, boron is commonly found in sedimentary rocks and exists in soils in the form of minerals such as **tourmaline, datolite, borax, asharite**, and as **boric acid**.

Molybdenum (Mo)

The amount of molybdenum in the soil is relatively low, approximately $3 \times 10^{-4}\%$. In soils rich in organic matter, Mo^{6+} is reduced to Mo^{2+} , making it part of a group of weakly mobile elements. Mo^{6+} is more mobile in neutral and slightly alkaline soils, making it more readily available for plant uptake. An excess of manganese (Mn) can lead to a deficiency of molybdenum and vice versa.

Molybdenum is particularly beneficial for crops such as **cauliflower, sugar beet, cotton, and legumes**. However, excessive Mo can cause **molybdenum toxicosis** in animals. This is often observed in **alkaline and calcareous soils** where Mo is more abundant. In healthy plants, the Mo content ranges from **3–4 mg/kg**, whereas in affected plant species, it can be as high as **33–38 mg/kg**.

Manganese (Mn)

According to V.I. Vernadsky, the average manganese content in soils is about $8.5 \times 10^{-2}\%$ [2]. The mobile fraction of this element comprises only **1–10%** of its total amount. In soils with weak alkaline reactions, $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2$ is formed, which is poorly absorbed by plants. In weakly alkaline and neutral environments, Mn oxidizes to MnO_2 , leading to manganese deficiency symptoms in plants.

Mn is an essential component of several enzymes. When deficient, plants may exhibit **necrosis** on leaves, eventually leading to plant death. In grain crops, **greyish spots** appear, a phenomenon observed in the **Fergana Valley**, where this research was conducted. In fruit trees, **chlorosis** is a common symptom [11, 12].

Copper (Cu)

The total copper content in soils is about $2 \times 10^{-3}\%$, with only about **1%** present in a mobile and available form. Copper is a crucial element for plant life and plays a key role in the structure of the enzyme **polyphenol oxidase**. The availability of Cu is closely linked to **photosynthesis** through **chloroplast activity**. It has been proven by **M.A. Pankov** [6] that in **calcareous soils**, copper is poorly absorbed by plants.

A **deficiency of copper (Cu)** in organisms can lead to **enzootic ataxia**, while an **excess** of it can cause diseases such as **anemia** and **hepatitis**.

Zinc (Zn)

The average content of this element in soil is about $5 \times 10^{-3}\%$, with only around **1%** present in a mobile form. In plants, zinc levels typically reach about $3 \times 10^{-4}\%$. Zinc is involved in the composition of several enzymes, and many plants have a high demand for it. These include **cotton, maize, apple, grape**, and others.

The microelements mentioned above are widely used in **cotton cultivation**. One of the most effective ways to utilize these elements is by studying both the **total and mobile forms** in the soil, as well as their **migration pathways** in the soil→plant→food→human chain [10].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research, the field studies were conducted based on the “Methodology of conducting field experiments” of the former Uzbek Cotton Growing Research Institute, and analyzes were conducted based on “Guidelines for the chemical analysis of soils” by E.V. Arinushkina. Systematic geochemical approaches of A.I. Perelman (1975) and M.A. Glazovskaya (1976) were used. The mathematical-statistical analyses of the results obtained were calculated by the dispersion method using the manual “Methods of field experience” by B.A. Dospekhov and Microsoft Excel.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In **Fergana region**, where our research was conducted, the **biomicroelement composition of light-colored sierozem soils** is illustrated in **Figure 1**. According to the data, the quantities of **Cu, Zn, Mn, B, and Mo** are distributed according to specific regularities that correspond to their individual characteristics and the properties of the soil.

It is known that **copper (Cu)** exists in nature in free forms Cu^0 , Cu^+ , and **mostly as Cu^{2+}** . In our case, this corresponds to the **plow layer and depths of 120–170 (180) cm**. The **concentration of Cu** is influenced by the presence of its precipitants such as **carbonates, sulfates, and oxides** [13, 14]. Cu^{2+} is also easily **sorbed by humus and colloids**, which limits its mobility. In total, **198 copper minerals** have been identified, most commonly forming **carbonate, sulfate, silicate, and phosphate compounds**.

Another **chalcophile element** is **zinc (Zn)**, which is also used in agriculture as a microelement. The **clarke value** of zinc is approximately $8.3 \times 10^{-3}\%$. According to **Perelman A.I.**, zinc replaces Fe and Mn in **micas and amphiboles** [7]. There are **66 known minerals** that contain zinc. However, in **slightly alkaline soils**, zinc becomes difficult for plants to absorb. Soils of this type include **carbonate soils**, which are widespread in **Fergana region** where we conducted our research. As a result, many **plants growing in light-colored sierozem soils in Fergana** consistently experience **zinc deficiency**.

Figure 1. Biomicroelement composition of light-colored sierozem soils in the Fergana region

Another important microelement for fruit trees and cotton cultivation is manganese (Mn). Manganese occurs widely in the Earth's crust in its 2+, 3+, and 4+ valence states. Its variable

valency leads to different behaviors in terms of mobility. Therefore, Mn participates with varying degrees of activity in oxidation-reduction processes, and in oxidizing and evaporative barriers, leading to accumulation in different forms and quantities. Mn^{2+} is considered the most mobile form compared to other manganese cations. Its clarke value is $1 \times 10^{-10}\%$, and over 120 mineral forms of manganese have been identified. Mn is especially accumulated by reeds.

In the light-colored sierozem soils of the Fergana region, where we conducted our study, Mn is considered a low-mobility element, and fruit plants frequently experience manganese deficiency. Among the anionogenic lithophile elements, boron (B) holds an important place. Like the elements mentioned above, boron is critical for fruit trees, vegetables, and melons. The B^{3+} ion does not exhibit metallic characteristics and is regarded as one of the most essential non-metal microelements. Its oxygen compounds are widely distributed, and calcium and magnesium borates are insoluble in water. Boron, like other elements, tends to accumulate in evaporative barriers and primarily moves in soils in the form of the BO_3^{3-} ion.

In the light-colored sierozem soils of the Fergana region, calcium acts as a major barrier in boron migration. Therefore, even though the total amount of boron in these soils may be high, plants still experience a significant demand for it during their growth and development. Like boron, molybdenum (Mo) also accumulates in the light-colored sierozem soils of the Fergana region and can exist in both anion and cation forms. However, as the cultivation intensity of the soil increases, the amount of molybdenum tends to decrease.

When evaluating the mobile forms of these elements, based on the classification of Kruglova E.K. and Aliyeva M., the following can be concluded (see Table 1):

In the plow and sub-plow layers of the light-colored sierozem soils studied in Fergana region, Cu, Zn, Mn, and B are found in relatively optimal amounts, whereas Mo is considered insufficient.

If we compare the amount of bio micronutrients in soils with the permissible concentrations established in V.G. Mineev's table, the following situation can be observed [8].

Table 1

Degree of plant provision with micronutrients (mg/kg)

Provision level	Cu	Zn	Mn	B	Mo ^x
Insufficient	<0,4	<1,5	<80,0	<0,8	<0,15
Adequate / Within Norm	0,4-0,8	1,5-2,5	80-100	0,8-1,8	0,15-0,3
High	0,8-1,0	>2,5	101-150	1,2-3,0	0,3-0,5
Saturated (or Oversupplied Province)	>1,0	-	>150	>3,0	>0,5

According to Mox A.S. Fatryanov, L.M. Voykin, and V.P. Madanov (1972), the amount of microelements such as Cu, Zn, B, Mo, and Mn in soils is lower than the standard values, i.e., 2–50, 10–300, 10–500, and 1–5 mg/kg, respectively. This indicates that in the soils of the Fergana Valley where our research was conducted, the mobile content of these microelements is significantly below these norms.

However, in the foothill pastures located in the region of light-colored sierozem soils of the Fergana region, the levels of Cu are high, and the contents of Zn, Mn, B, and Mo are at high or saturated province levels. If livestock graze in these pastures, then we should expect some

animal diseases caused by excess or deficiency of these microelements. This is because these microelements can enter the human body through the meat, milk, and dairy products of livestock and may cause certain diseases.

An analysis of the chemical elements in the human diet shows that the calcium content in winter-spring season is 78.5% in men and 75.4% in women, while in the summer-autumn season, it decreases to 65.6% and 62.4%, respectively. Other microelements appear in the following proportions: phosphorus – 70.9–70.2% in men and 66.9–65.4% in women; magnesium – 88.6–86.3% in men and 77.8–79.2% in women; iron – 68.0–65.0% in men and 74.0–73.0% in women [9].

Ensuring the population's access to ecologically clean food products requires a thorough study of the movement, accumulation, and other migration processes of chemical elements in the **soil → plant → animal world → food product → human chain**. It is a pressing issue to prevent certain endemic diseases that may arise as a result.

CONCLUSIONS

For obtaining abundant yields from crops grown under the natural conditions of the light-colored sierozem soils in Fergana region, and to produce ecologically clean food products with balanced levels of proteins, starch, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals, it is of great importance to study the migration of chemical elements in the **soil → plant → food product → human body chain**.

Under the natural conditions of the light-colored sierozem soils of the Fergana region, there are provinces where the levels of microelements exceed the norm as well as those where they are deficient. In such areas, there is a high probability of the emergence of certain endemic diseases that may pose a threat to human health, animal life, and plants. As a preventive measure against such risks, it would be advisable to develop **soil maps or digital maps** that provide information about these provinces.

It is crucial to prevent both the deficiency and the excess of microelement provinces. To achieve this, grazing of livestock by farms in these regions should be strictly regulated according to a predetermined plan. Moreover, in provinces where the microelement levels exceed the standard limits, it is essential to **select and cultivate plant species that have a high demand for these specific microelements**.

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